

WE CREATE WITH CERAMICS AT SCHOOL

Ing. Tatiana Uhríková

Constantine the Philosopher University in Nitra

Slovakia

E-mail: tanauhrikova@gmail.com

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Abstract: The current period of recent years brings a tangible and visible comeback of interest in traditions, crafts, handmade and folklore. Ceramics is a statement that fits into all areas. The article discusses about the reasons how ceramics entered into the Slovak school education system and the importance of its position in education, and compares the theoretical basis of the possibilities of working with ceramics with pupils at school with the real school life of Slovak teacher.

Keywords: ceramics, clay, education, school system, students, teacher, strategy.

Introduction

We could assume that a group of people who just look at these lines are fond of not only about the concept of ceramics, but also about the creative process with it. For many of us, ceramics has become not only a hobby, but we want to share it with others in our work. A great environment opens up for us, which brings many opportunities, views, enthusiasm, but also disappointments, problems and hardships - the school environment of a Slovak teacher and work with children. Ceramics can be used in so many fields that it was impossible to avoid the decision for the desire and hobby for it in the school environment, as Roeselová (2003) mentions in her book, that work and contact with plastic material has been very close to us since early childhood, when as small children we discovered the world around us using touch and pressure.

The term ceramics is a part of the theoretical basis of all areas and is intertwined with individual subjects in the educational system of primary education. However, we are faced with two worlds that we routinely encounter in the school educational system - theory versus practice. From a theoretical point of view, we should be familiar with clay - ceramics already at the beginning of education, not only theoretically, but also haptically, artistically, visually, aesthetically, craftily and practically. According to Homzová (2015), thanks to their own self-knowledge, the pupil creates mental and social prevention and strengthens their own identity. They can equal with difference more easily, learn to understand and cooperate. Or it can help us to more closely connect education to the pupil's personal experience and their own experiences, as Slavík (1997) understands creativity too.

In the current school system in Slovakia, abbreviated as ISCED, we encounter the term ceramics in many interdisciplinary connections - since ISCED (International Standard Classification of Education) has belonged to the international family of economic and social classifications of the United Nations, which are applied in global statistics with the aim of compiling, collecting and analyzing internationally comparable data. ISCED is a reference classification for organizing educational programs and relevant qualifications according to levels of education and fields of study. ISCED is the product of international agreement and is formally adopted by member states at the General Conference of UNESCO (Metodika mapovania, n.d.).

Material and methods

As the topic of ceramics gradually appears at school, it is necessary to indicate the smooth transitions of the educational levels that our children go through. We will present materials such as the Slovak school education system, which is divided into several levels starting from level 0 to level 8, currently the educational program is also divided in detail by the letters A - V, which cover individual disciplines in the given levels of education. The methodology of the research itself consists of the literary method, by which we process available information, and the method of a brief electronic questionnaire in the school environment of teachers.

Primary education is completed by children in primary schools. It is included in the two-level scale ISCED 1 and ISCED 2 - with ISCED 1 covering Primary Education, which represents grades 1-4 = children from 6 to 10 years old, the so-called First Level. After completing Primary Education, students proceed to Lower Secondary Education, which we call Second Level. This level is included in grades 5-9 = children from 11-15 years old. If students complete both levels, they will obtain Primary Education as you can see the sequence in Table 1 and can continue to Secondary Education.

Table 1 ISCED Primary education

	Level of education	Field code	ISCED
PRIMARY EDUCATION	PRIMARY EDUCATION 1st level	B	1
		C	
	LOWER SECONDARY EDUCATION 2nd level	D	2

Source <https://www.minedu.sk/data/files/3772.pdf>

The above-mentioned levels of education form the structure of the system, its content is filled by the State Educational Program of Schools, which is the hierarchically highest target program project of education according to the Education Act. It includes the framework model of the graduate, the framework curriculum of the school level and its framework curriculum. It expresses the main principles and goals of the state's educational policy, as well as the democratic and humanistic values on which national education is based. It defines the general goals of schools as key competencies (abilities), in the balanced development of the personality of students and the framework content of education. The State Educational Program supports a comprehensive approach to developing students' abilities to know, act, evaluate and communicate and understand each other at a given level of education. It is the starting point and binding document for the creation of an individual school educational program of a school, which takes into account specific local and regional conditions and needs (isced1, n.d.).

We come to the idea of local and regional conditions, which are more closely addressed in the documents of the School Educational Programs. Each school has the opportunity to modify the content of education with a focus on its usable possibilities, educates students with special educational needs, supports the socio-emotional climate with the school's own culture and its environment, focuses on the individual development of the personal potential of students, includes cross-cutting topics with overlaps of social, ecological, economic, ethical, financial,

political events, gives space through its own educational program to complete the content of education according to specific regional and local conditions and requirements, while building on the basic goals of the state educational program, since the school system, society, generations are elemental content, the School Educational Program is an open document that can be updated according to the needs of the school. Those options of the School Educational Program are selected in which the usability of the topic associated with the term ceramics is offered. The basement of the ŠkVP is the Framework Curriculum (RUP) shown in Table 2, which outlines the educational areas into which individual subjects are incorporated - as interdisciplinarity enters between individual subjects - the term ceramics is represented in the context of each subject.

Table 2 Framework Curriculum (RUP) for Primary School

educational field	teaching subject	year of primary education					vintage lower secondary education					
		1.	2.	3.	4.	Σ	5.	6.	7.	8.	9.	Σ
Language and communication	Slovak language and literature	9	8	7	7	31	5	5	4	5	5	24
	English language			3	3	6	3	3	3	3	3	15
Mathematics and working with information	mathematics	4	4	4	4	16	4	4	4	4	5	21
	informatics			1	1	2	1	1	1	1		4
Man and nature	first grader	1	2			3						
	natural science			1	2	3						
	physics							2	1	2	1	6
	chemistry								2	2	1	5
	biology						2	1	2	1	1	7
Man and society	native science			1	2	3						
	history						1	1	1	1	2	6
	geography						2	1	1	1	1	6
	civics							1	1	1	1	4
Man and values	ethical education/religious education/religion	1	1	1	1	4	1	1	1	1	1	5
Man and the world of work	work teaching			1	1	2						
	technique						1	1	1	1	1	5
Art and culture	music education	1	1	1	1	4	1	1	1	1		4
	art education	2	2	1	1	6	1	1	1	1	1	5
Health and movement	physical and sports education	2	2	2	2	8	2	2	2	2	2	10
	basis	20	20	23	25	88	24	25	26	27	25	127
	optional (available) hours	2	3	2	1	8	3	4	4	3	5	19
	together	22	23	25	26	96	27	29	30	30	30	146

Source https://www.statpedu.sk/files/articles/dokumenty/inovovany-statny-vzdelavaci-program/rup_zs_pre-z-s-vyu_ovac_m-jazykom-slovensk_m.pdf

You can see the ceramics is encountered at least in every educational area. It is not strictly necessary to include it only in art education, whose time allocation is 1 hour per week at the 2nd level, as the RUP shows, which is a very weak support for creative activity. Individual subjects meet the content and performance standards that determine its goals. The following table shows in which subjects at primary school students will come into contact with the topic of ceramics. Table 3 shows the term actually occurring in the school state content of education, however, when creating their own thematic plan associated with the preparation, the teacher can use and insert the term ceramics into any topic and carry out a meaningful, activating, experiential lesson in which students will encounter not only theory, but also practical skills (inovovaný isced1, n.d.).

Table 3 Occurrence of the term ceramics in individual educational areas and their subjects of primary education, source author

EDUCATION AREA	SUBJECT	TERM CERAMICS
LANGUAGE AND COMMUNICATION	SLOVAK LANGUAGE	5th grade – declension of sub-nouns 7th grade – repetition of a sentence 9th grade – sentence elements
	ENGLISH LANGUAGE	8th grade - professional terminology – materials, article 9th grade – Ecology – Clay and its importance
MATHEMATICS AND WORKING WITH INFORMATION	MATHEMATICS	-
	INFORMATICS	-
MAN AND NATURE	FIRST SCIENCE	-
	NATURAL SCIENCE	-
	PHYSICS	-
	CHEMISTRY	8th grade – chemical elements contained in clay and firing into ceramics – chemical reactions
	BIOLOGY	8th and 9th grade – pedology, geology – clay for pottery
MAN AND SOCIETY	COUNTRY SCIENCE	3rd grade – monuments of Slovakia
	HISTORY	5th and 6th grade – prehistory and first tools, utility items
	GEOGRAPHY	8th grade – Industry and Areas with Finds
	SOCIETY SCIENCE	-
MAN AND VALUES	ETHICS	-
	RELIGIOUS EDUCATION	Pottery of humanity
MAN AND THE WORLD OF WORK	WORK EDUCATION	3rd grade – properties of materials, crafts, production of traditional products

		4th grade – folk crafts - pottery
	TECHNICS	5th grade– craft, materials 7th grade – technical materials Working with non-traditional material
ART AND CULTURE	MUSIC	-
	ART	1st grade – artists – ceramicists 3rd grade – stories on ceramic vases 5th grade – mosaic, suggestions of pottery
HEALTH AND EXERCISE	PHYSICAL AND SPORTS EDUCATION	-

Source Author

Results

Slovak School is truly a place where we find overlaps of many concepts that cooperate with all areas and subjects as well, including our target term ceramics. After completing the basic available theoretical foundations that bring us closer to understanding the reason why ceramics is so fascinating and enchanting, we come to a practical and realistic picture of working with ceramics at school with children. The task and duty of every teacher is to meet the content and achievement standards contained in subjects by using appropriately chosen forms and methods of his work. This means that if a topic related to ceramics appears in a given subject - the teacher will cover the topic - verbally, with demonstrations, a project, a homework assignment, or skip the topic... BECAUSE THERE IS NO RELATION TO IT. Based on this statement, I consider the teacher's passion for the given issue - which is ceramics for us - to be the most important step. If this point is met, everything goes easier and the path is simpler.

Working with ceramics at school can be achieved in several ways:

- directly in the classroom as experiential learning, (by staging method, demonstration),
- through a circle activity, proposed at the beginning of the school year as part of your school's Work Plan,
- by visiting a nearby ceramic studio - the chosen form of teaching,
- cooperation with external institutions operating in the field of working with ceramics
- Leisure Centers, Elementary Art Schools, Social Service Homes, Regional Educational Centers, with another school....

We can suppose that by reading this article, you are creative and inventive person inclined to meaningful work with children and you are interested in developing rich artistic activities at school - perhaps you are wondering how to achieve this - we do not have a kiln for firing ceramics, we do not have the material, there is no place... With the above-mentioned lines, you can avoid these skeptical thoughts.

To clarify the facts, the questions were asked in the form of a simple questionnaire via email communication with a sample of 55 random selected elementary schools from all over Slovakia, of which 5 have a kiln for firing ceramics, some schools try to create with modeling clay, they cooperate poorly with other institutions... it was not possible to evaluate the questionnaire in a high-quality and accurate way, because a response was not received from many elementary schools which were contacted.

- Kiln for firing ceramics – if your school does not have the financial resources to afford a kiln, use various project calls aimed at developing

and supporting culture, traditions and crafts. These goals are currently the content of many projects from various institutions that prepare the projects.

- Afternoon ceramics courses – through the school courses activity it is possible to use EDUCATIONAL VOUCHERS that support your school by finance from the state, the funds can be used for the material necessary for working with ceramics.
- Cooperation - everyone will be inclined to cooperate with external institutions and you will gain students, they will get to know the new environment, friends, colleagues, you will make your school more visible, you will present your work.
- Parents' Association - you can also find support in the school's organisations such as the Parents' Association, which can cover the costs of materials or expenses related to students' travel documents.

Conclusion

It is a very simple to say how something should be done – many of us know the theory – but the path of reality is often thorny, full of obstacles and logs underfoot. At the Primary School, Lipová 183, we have been working with ceramics since 2018, it has become a part of our school life. In 2014, we created a new School Educational System characteristic of our small municipal school and the logo itself, which symbolizes the educational strategy – JUEMI – each letter is the leader of the area we emphasize – Languages, ART, Ecology, Mathematics and Information and Communication Technologies. I would like to state that it is the area of art and ceramics in it that has moved our school progressively forward. Thanks to the following specific steps and procedures, we get to know each other better, cooperate, develop, rejoice, enjoy and travel, and we have managed to live with ceramics every day:

- competitions (In the land of crafts, Artistic spectrum, The universe through the eyes of children),
- exhibitions (Christmas town, Fruit and vegetable exhibition, Ceramics in the bookshop, Mother's Day),
- course activities (KERAMIKA course),
- cooperation with institutions (DSS Lipka, we started with them - we did not have a kiln for firing ceramics. Clients - disabled boys, mental diseases - created once a week together with our pupils in the KERAMIKA course and then, after drying, we fired our works together in their kiln. DSS Jesenka, CVČ Šurany, Záhradkári Lipová, Nitrianska galéria, ROS Nové Zámky),
- peer learning (older ones help to finish the works of the younger ones, in case of a time deficit, we finish the works of each other, we use the work of other subjects),
- school events (School ball, gift for seniors, first-year students, DOD, Easter decorations, Halloween, end of school year),
- presentation of the school at markets (Šuriansky jarmok, Porcinkula NZ, Cedron Nitrava, Nitriansky jarmok, Lipovské trhy),
- school craft courses (during the holidays we meet, create, invite surrounding schools to create together),
- workshops (we spend the afternoons inviting friends and fans of ceramics - we learn from each other - children, adults and vice versa),
- projects (we follow the calls of various organizations for the development of our studio – I constantly collect suggestions, inspirations from students, which would enrich our work,

- needs and imagination to encourage creativity and a taste for work),
- materials (clay, glazes, tools) financed from educational vouchers and contributions from parents in the form of a financial donation to support children's ceramics,
- presentation in the press - regularly in the regional magazine Žurnál, the website of municipality, the school, the school magazine Školoviny, social networks, our own channels with parents, pupils,
- a qualified and enthusiastic teacher (2 qualified teachers at the 2nd level),
- and last but not least, what can be considered the most important strong point – is the support from the school management, the relationship to art, the sense of aesthetics, the feeling of artistic culture, the artephyletic approach to education,
- at our school, my person is in charge, I am the director, who is open to all new challenges, approaches, supporting children's personalities, revealing children's strengths.

Many times, this is achieved precisely thanks to working with ceramics, and the children find unknown things in themselves that will help them choose their path through their young lives and give them strength in expressing their personality. Reflection comes when more than half of the school's students regularly sign up for your group, when children win competitions with their works, when your school is full of ceramics decorations of your pupils works, when you give gifts to your loved ones at school events, you feel and see joy and your work... makes sense - thanks to CERAMICS.

Results in pictures

Picture 1 The winning work of our student
In the competition „In the land of craft“

Picture 2 Our table made by our students
in front of our art studio

Picture 3 Ceramic hearts for „Valentine school ball“

Picture 4 Working in the studio

Picture 5 Works from fresh clay in the course KERAMIKA

Picture 6 Fruit for exhibition „Fruit and Vegetable“

Picture 7 Piggies for happiness at Christmas time

Picture 8 Creative skills

Picture 9 Fresh clay works on the kiln

All the pictures made by author with parents' agreement of the children.

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Appendix 1

Participation form

Author (full name)	Tatiana Uhríková
Organization (workplace)	Department of Technology and Information Technologies
Address	Department of Technology and Information Technologies Faculty of Education Dražovská cesta 4 949 01 Nitra Slovakia
Position	PhD. student
Academic degree, title	Ing. Tatiana Uhríková
Material title (article)	We create with ceramics at school
Section title (direction)	
Form of participation (offline or online)	online
Contact phone number	+421 903 789 128
Email	tanauhrikova@gmail.com